

The Time Independent Schrodinger Equation as Free Energy Equal to Zero for the Ground State Oscillator

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In a previous note, it was shown that for a free quantum particle in a box with only kinetic energy, one could apply the thermodynamic relationship $dU=TdS$ to obtain $f_p \cdot f_p = \exp(-p^2/2mT)$ i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor. In this case, a wavefunction of $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$ was actually used (instead of the usual approach of density = $\sum_p \exp(-p^2/2mT) \sin(px)\sin(px)$). It was noted that if the box length becomes large, $W(x)$ approaches a Gaussian which is the ground state solution of the oscillator problem. The oscillator ground state solution, however, is obtained solving the time-independent Schrodinger equation for $V(x)=Cx^2$. This raises a question. Why should the thermodynamic equation $dU=TdS$ (for zero work) have any connection with the time-independent Schrodinger equation? In another previous note, it was shown that for the oscillator, kinetic energy density in momentum space summed over p is proportional to Shannon's entropy for momentum i.e. $\sum_p 2f_p \ln(f_p)$. It was also shown that $W(x)W(x)V(x)$ for the oscillator is proportional to spatial entropy $d(x) \ln[d(x)]$, where $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$ using Shannon's entropy. Thus, a connection between classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics seems to exist for the oscillator ground state. In this note, we wish to show that the Schrodinger equation in momentum space is equivalent to a free energy equal to zero for the case of pure kinetic motion. This explains, it seems, why the temperature dependent wavefunction for a free gas without a potential is equivalent to the ground state of an oscillator.

Free Gas in Thermodynamics

Consider a one dimensional gas of particles at temperature T , with F_p being the probability of having p . Then, from thermodynamics $dU=TdS$ if there is no work done. If one uses Shannon's entropy for momentum then:

$$S = -k \sum_p F_p \ln[F_p] \quad \text{Let us consider } k=1 \text{ here. } ((1))$$

$$\text{Then: } dS = \sum_p dF_p \{ 1 + \ln(F_p) \} \quad \text{while} \quad U = \sum_p p^2/2m F_p \text{ so}$$

$$dU = \sum_p p^2/2m dF_p$$

This leads to: $F_p = C \exp(-p^2/2mT)$ where T is a constant.

This approach was applied in (1) to a quantum particles in a box with no potential. In such a case, the traditional solution $d(x) = \sum_p \exp(-p^2/2mT) \sin(px)\sin(px)$ with $p=6.28 n/L$ was

not used. Rather a wavefunction was defined as $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$. In momentum space, the energy is given by $\sum_p f_p^* f_p p^2/2m$ and using $dU = TdS$ one was able to obtain $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$ with $f_p = \exp(-p^2/b)$ with b as a constant related to energy.

For L , the size of the box, becoming infinite, $W(x)$ becomes a Gaussian $\exp(-ax^2)$ which is identical to the ground state of a quantum oscillator. It should be noted here that

$$F = U - TS \quad \text{the free energy} \quad ((2))$$

For this example, in momentum space one has:

$$U = \sum_p f_p^* f_p p^2/2m \quad \text{with } f_p = f_p^* f_p$$

$$\text{Now } TS = -T \sum_p f_p \ln(f_p) = \sum_p -p^2/2m f_p$$

Thus, $F = U - TS = 0$ for this case.

Time Independent Schrodinger Equation and the Ground State of the Oscillator

It was argued in (2) that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which differs from classical statistical mechanics. In classical statistical mechanics, one wishes to have a constant temperature everywhere which leads to a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ everywhere, even if there is a potential. The effect of the potential is to add the factor $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ regardless of the potential. Quantum mechanics is not like this, it aims at creating an energy density $E(x) = E W(x)W(x)$ at each point in space, so the potential $V(x)$ is very important in governing the form of f_p in $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$. Here $W(x)$ and f_p are Fourier transforms of each other. For the oscillator ground state one has $\exp(-bp^2) = f_p$ and $W(x) = \exp(-ax^2)$ where a and b are related constants (and related to energy). One may wonder why $f_p^* f_p$ and $W(x)^* W(x)$ mimic the statistical mechanical results for an oscillator. One may also wonder why $f_p = \exp(-bp^2)$ mimics the general case of a statistical mechanical distribution for momentum.

Consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ written as Fourier series. Then:

$$\sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j \exp(ipx) + (1/2m) p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx) = E f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ can be cancelled from both sides of ((3)) and both sides multiplied by f_p .

Let us consider the term: $1/2m p^2/2m f_p^* f_p$. In quantum mechanics one tries to find a set of f_p values such that ((3)) will be satisfied with E depending on the f_p 's. This is difficult and leads to discrete values for E , each for a different set of f_p 's.

Let us ask if there might be a case in which $f_p \cdot f_p = \exp(-p^2/2mT)$ or $f_p = \exp(-p^2/4mT)$? If this were the case, then the kinetic energy term would interestingly become Shannon's entropy for momentum.

Then ((3)) summed over all p would lead to:

$$V = E - T \text{ Shannon's Entropy for momentum} \quad ((4))$$

where Shannon's entropy = $- \sum f_p \ln[f_p]$ with $F_p = f_p \cdot f_p$

This can be rewritten as:

$$0 = (E - V) - T \text{ Shannon's Entropy for momentum} = \text{Kinetic energy} - T \text{ Shannon's entropy}$$

or

Free energy for a particle with no potential = 0.

This is the result from classical statistical mechanics for particles with no potential.

In quantum mechanics, however, $f_p = \exp(-b p^2)$ implies $W(x) = \exp(-a x^2)$. This is ground state solution for an oscillator potential with $2a - 4a^2 x^2 = \text{kinetic energy}$ and $4a^2 x^2 = \text{potential energy}$ and $E = 2a$.

Thus, the ground state oscillator in momentum space is mathematically equivalent to a classical statistical mechanical case of a gas with no potential for which free energy is 0.

Ground State Oscillator

Interestingly, for the ground state oscillator, the time independent Schrodinger equation is of the form:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy for momentum} + C \text{ Shannon's entropy for position} = E \quad ((5))$$

With $\text{Shannon's entropy for momentum} = \sum_p f_p \ln(f_p)$

And $\text{Shannon's entropy for position} = \int dx W(x) \ln[W(x)]$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this short note we have tried to explain why $f_p = \exp(-p^2/b)$ for the ground state oscillator solution matches the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for momentum in classical statistical mechanics. We argue that the time-independent Schrodinger equation in momentum

space becomes equivalent to $F=E-TS$ with S being given by Shannon's entropy for momentum, namely $-2fp \ln[fp]$ summed over all p 's.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Temperature Dependent Schrodinger Equation and a Particle in a Box (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Bound State Quantum Mechanics as a Statistical Theory in Momentum Space? (preprint, zenodo, 2019)